

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Mauno, S. (2024). Coping with Technostress in the Software Industry: Coping Strategies and Factors Underlying their Selection (Online Replication Package) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14180104>

In this questionnaire, we ask you to describe one exceptionally burdensome/stressful experience related to the use of technology or software in your work. Experiences can be related to, for example, using a work computer, phone, or software in your work tasks.

The questionnaire takes about 15 minutes to complete.

The answers will be treated confidentially. You can read the privacy policy here [[link to the privacy policy](#)].

Thank you for your participation!

Background information

Age: *[open field, including an option "I prefer not to disclose"]*

Nationality: *[open field, including an option "I prefer not to disclose"]*

Gender:

- Male
- Female
- Other
- I prefer not to disclose

Employment status:

- Employed full-time (30+ hours a week)
- Employed part-time (less than 30 hours a week)
- Entrepreneur
- Freelancer
- Unemployed
- I prefer not to disclose

Job title: *[open field, including an option "I prefer not to disclose"]*

Work experience in current role (in years): *[open field, including an option "I prefer not to disclose"]*

[Other questions not relevant here e.g., the respondents' Prolific ID for them to claim their monetary reward.]

Burdensome/stressful experience

Please take a moment to recall an exceptionally burdensome/stressful experience related to the use of technology or software in your work. You can take a few minutes to recall. This time is allowed for in the duration of the questionnaire.

Technology and/or software that was involved in the experience: *[open question]*

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Please describe the burdensome/stressful experience in as much detail as possible in your own words: *[open question]*

For how long did the experience last?

- Less than one hour
- 1–12 hours
- 13–24 hours
- 1–7 days
- 1–4 weeks
- Over one month
- I don't know

How long ago did the experience occur?

- Less than two weeks ago
- 2–4 weeks ago
- 1–3 months ago
- 4–12 months ago
- Over one year ago
- I don't know

How would you evaluate the strain caused by the experience?

- Very low
- Fairly low
- Moderate
- Fairly high
- Very high
- I don't know

How did you try to reduce or mitigate the effects of the burdensome/stressful experience?
[open question]

[This is an attention check question] What is this writing task about? Please choose one of the following options:

- stressful experiences at work
- cooking
- studying abroad
- the meaning of life

Thank you for participating in the questionnaire!

Confirm your submission by using the link below:

[Using the link, respondents were able to confirm on Prolific that they had completed the questionnaire in order to receive their monetary reward, following Prolific's guidelines.]

[The outline of the questionnaire is presented regarding the parts relevant to the current study. The questionnaire also included other questions, which are not presented here.]